

Permeability of Electrolytes Through Polystyrene Supported Aluminium Hydroxide Membrane

W. U. MALIK*, J. S. TYAGI**, R. K. GULATI and SAT PAUL ARORA

Chemical Laboratories, M. L. N. College, Yamuna Nagar

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The permeability and membrane potential of various electrolytes through polystyrene supported aluminium hydroxide membrane were investigated. The order of permeability was $\text{Na}^+ > \text{K}^+ > \text{Li}^+$ and $\text{Ca}^{++} > \text{Ba}^{++}$ while the membrane potential was found to be of reverse order. The energy of activation and entropy change for diffusion process for various electrolytes were found to be between 4 to 7 K cal/mole and -7 to -18 E.U./mole respectively.

INVESTIGATIONS on permeability of ions through membranes were carried out with ever interesting vigour by many eminent physical chemists, biochemists and bio-engineers¹⁻³ to give a clear understanding of the real mechanism of the transport phenomenon through membranes. Malik and coworkers⁴⁻⁶ described it as colloid-chemical phenomenon. Similar approach was made by Lakshminarayanaiah⁷ and coworkers. We, during the course of our studies on the permeability of electrolytes through inorganic membranes deduced a simple relationship between permeability and membrane potential giving a simple picture of the transport phenomenon across polystyrene supported inorganic membranes.

The present communication deals with the permeability data of various electrolytes, thermodynamic parameters of the diffusion process and membrane potential values for polystyrene supported aluminium hydroxide membrane.

Experimental

Preparation of membranes: About 4.0 gm aluminium hydroxide gel was prepared by mixing 500 ml of 0.1 M aluminium chloride (A.R.) solution with excess of 20% ammonia solution. The gel was thoroughly washed with double distilled water and was dried at 120° for about 6 hours. The gel was homogenised with 200 mesh size polystyrene powder in the ratio 4 : 1 by weight for about half an hour. 1.5 gm homogenised mixture was heated gradually upto 125° in a die of specimen mount press under pressure ranging between 6500-7500 psi. Then the die was slowly cooled down to room temperature and the membrane, 2.5 cm in diameter and 0.1 cm in thickness was obtained. Three membranes were prepared in this way and were put under high power microscope to check up any deformity and cracks.

Permeability measurements: Willis⁹ constant flow method was employed for permeability

measurements. The permeability cell consisted of twin flat glass (pyrex) vessels with flanges ground together. The diameter of each half cell was 2.5 cm and giving a volume of 20 ml. The membrane in required cationic form was cemented in between the two half cells with an adhesive (Araldite). 0.5M solution of the electrolyte was allowed to flow continuously to the top of the cell in the same manner as the conductivity water for the lower half. The hydrostatic pressure on each side of the membrane was always kept equal by adjusting the rate of flow of the solution and conductivity water across the membrane. The rate of flow was maintained at 100 ml per hour. The effluent coming out of the lower half cell was analysed conductometrically. By knowing the rate of flow and concentration of the effluent, (from concentration-conductance curves) the permeability (p) in millimoles per hour was determined at 20, 25, 30 and 35°. The results in the form of plots between log p against 1/T (p and T being permeability and absolute temperature respectively) are given in Fig. 1.

Membrane potential measurements: The membrane in requisite cationic form was connected to one end of a pyrex glass tube and the tube was inserted in a corked beaker provided with two holes. Solutions of different concentrations of electrolytes were filled in the tube and the beaker. The membrane potentials were determined with the help of a reference electrode (SCE) kept dipped in the two solutions. All the measurements were made at $25 \pm 1^\circ$.

Results and Discussion

Considering the permeability of different electrolytes for the membrane under study, it is seen that the order of permeability values for various cations is $\text{Na}^+ > \text{K}^+ > \text{Li}^+$ for alkali metals and $\text{Ca}^{++} > \text{Ba}^{++}$ for alkaline earth metals.

* Vice-Chancellor, Bundelkhand University, Jhansi (India).

** Lecturer, Meerut College, Meerut (India).

Fig. 1. Variation in permeability (millimoles per hour) with temperature (absolute degree) in the presence of different electrolytes with aluminium hydroxide membrane.
(1) LiCl, (2) NaCl, (3) KCl, (4) BaCl₂, (5) CaCl₂.

The various factors which control electrolyte permeability through a membrane are the charge on the membrane, its porosity, the charge and size of the diffusing ion and adsorption. Over and above these, another factor which should be added is exchange capacity of the membrane material.

The fixed charges on the membrane act in two ways: firstly, they exclude the coions from the membrane phase due to electrostatic repulsion and secondly, increase the mobility of counter ions towards it. Thus the fast moving chloride ions would be excluded from the membrane phase whereas the slow moving cations such as Li⁺, Ca⁺⁺, etc., would be attracted towards the membrane. The next two steps to follow are (i) entry of the cations into the membrane phase by ion exchange with the counter ions and (ii) diffusion of these ions to the other side through the pores of the membrane. This would eventually lead to the setting up of an electrical double layer across the membrane and giving rise to equilibrium conditions.

The transference of ions through the membrane is influenced by the size of the hydrated ion. Hydrated ions would be less exchangeable than the less hydrated one and would consequently show smaller diffusion through the pores. There would, however, be one opposing factor, viz., smaller ion association due to hydration which facilitates the permeation. But the combined effect of the former two factors would outweigh the latter factor with the result that the hydrated ions would permeate with a slower rate than the unhydrated or less hydrated ones.

An altogether different behaviour, which is rather difficult to explain is that strongly hydrated Ca⁺⁺ show greater permeability than the less hydrated Ba⁺⁺. A similar behaviour was observed by Gregor¹⁰ in case of weak acid cation exchange resins containing carboxylate anions. According to Mullin¹¹ the hydration of the materials of the pores themselves may provide a favourable water environment for particular ions, so that they step into the pore away from their water molecules with which they were already associated before entering the membrane phase. This would result in selection of a particular size with discrimination against both smaller and larger hydrated ions. A condition of dynamic equilibrium is set up so that a fraction, *f*, of the number of given kind of particles in the solution has a reduced hydration corresponding to excess energy, *E_a*, per mole according to Boltzmann distribution law. It appears that the fraction, *f*, of ions losing water of hydration on coming in contact with the pore material is higher in the case of Ca⁺⁺ than Ba⁺⁺ with the result that the former gets easily diffused than the latter. It is worth pointing out that the size of the unhydrated Ca⁺⁺ ion (0.99Å) is much smaller than Ba⁺⁺ (1.35Å)¹² and therefore its permeability through the pores will also be favoured once it has left its rigid hydration shell.

The values of membrane potential across the membrane under study are given in Table 1. The results reveal that the membrane potentials follow

TABLE 1—POTENTIALS OF ALUMINIUM HYDROXIDE MEMBRANE

Inside solution conc. Outside solution conc.	Observed potentials in (mv) in various electrolytes				
	LiCl	NaCl	KCl	BaCl ₂	CaCl ₂
1.0/0.1(M)	50.0	18.9	21.2	25.1	22.5
0.5/0.05	49.0	25.0	25.3	24.2	21.7
0.2/0.02	47.5	30.6	33.9	23.8	21.0
0.1/0.01	45.0	32.2	36.6	23.2	20.1
0.05/0.005	40.0	40.6	41.4	22.0	19.0
0.02/0.002	36.8	46.8	44.0	21.0	18.5
0.01/0.001	32.0	48.0	45.3	20.1	18.0
0.005/0.0005	29.0	—	47.6	19.0	17.0

the order :

Li⁺ > K⁺ > Na⁺ in 1 : 1 and Ba⁺⁺ > Ca⁺⁺ in 2 : 1 electrolytes. The order remains practically constant over a wide conc. range 1.0 to 0.1 M for all electrolytes. Also the order is just reverse of the permeability values for the membrane. The magnitude of the membrane potential depends on (i) preferential adsorption of anions of the diffusion electrolyte on the membrane surface, (ii) exchangeability of cations, (iii) the size of the hydrated cations and (iv) potential across the membrane (diffusion potential).

Preferential adsorption of the anions would enhance the negative charge on the membrane. The cations would enter the membrane phase after

exchange adsorption with the counter ions. The number of cations thus entering would depend on their relative exchangeability with respect to the particular membrane. Li⁺ showing the least exchangeability would be lesser in number in the membrane phase in comparison to K⁺ or Na⁺. The net negative charge on the membrane would thus be higher in the case of Li⁺. K⁺ with higher exchangeability would develop a lesser negative charge than Li⁺ and Na⁺ with still higher exchangeability would develop the least charge on the membrane. Similarly Ba⁺⁺ with lesser exchangeability than Ca⁺⁺ develops a higher membrane potential than that of Ca⁺⁺ is explainable on the above consideration.

Various values of thermodynamic parameters are listed in Table 2. Applying Boltzmann's distribution law, $f = e^{-E_a/RT}$ to hydration-dehydration dynamic equilibrium, it can be said that at higher temperature considerably higher fraction of the

TABLE 2—EXPERIMENTAL ACTIVATION ENERGY E_a AND OTHER THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS CALCULATED FROM THE TRANSITION STATE THEORY OF THE RATE PROCESSES FOR ELECTROLYTE DIFFUSION THROUGH ALUMINIUM HYDROXIDE MEMBRANE

Electrolyte	E_a K cal	ΔH K cal	ΔF K cal	ΔS E.U.
LiCl	4.118	3.526	8.937	-18.158
NaCl	6.774	6.187	8.552	-7.936
KCl	4.486	3.894	8.743	-16.278
BaCl ₂	5.408	4.816	9.153	-14.560
CaCl ₂	5.071	4.479	9.005	-15.188

total number of ions would be unhydrated and would possess excess energy E_a required for permeation. The slope of $\log p$ vs $1/T$ plots ($E_a/2.303R$) gives the activation energy, E_a , required for diffusion process. The values lie between 4.118 K cal/mole to 6.774 K cal/mole. Obviously these values would be much higher than the values for activation energy for free diffusion of electrolytes due to membrane barrier.

Theory of absolute reaction rate to the process of diffusion rate was applied to calculate free energy change (ΔF) and other parameters through the following equations :

$$P' = \frac{\lambda^2 kT}{dh} e^{-\Delta F/RT} \quad \dots (1)$$

where λ =average distance between the equilibrium positions during the diffusion process and is equal to 3×10^{-8} cm (quoted for a membrane by Lai and Mortland^{1,2}), k =Boltzmann constant, d =thickness of membrane, h =Planck's constant, $R=1.987$ cal/degree/mole, T =temperature in

absolute degree. P' , the permeability is calculated from the equation,

$$P' = \frac{p \times 10^{-6}}{3.6 \times A \times \Delta C} \quad \dots (2)$$

where p =permeability in millimoles per hour, A =area of cross-section of the membrane, ΔC =difference in initial and final concentrations of the effluent.

The enthalpy change (ΔH) and entropy change (ΔS) of activation are related as follows :

$$E_a = \Delta H - \Delta nRT \quad \dots (3)$$

where $\Delta n = -1$

$$\text{and } \Delta F = \Delta H - T\Delta S \quad \dots (4)$$

The ΔS values for the present study are higher and negative as compared with parchment supported membranes⁷. This means permeation takes place without distorting or changing the membrane structure¹. It is understandable because the membrane unlike parchment supported one is mechanically very stable. Moreover, the linear relationship between $\log p$ and $1/T$ reveals that the membrane does not undergo any irreversible distortion or change in the structure. As regards negative ΔS values, these cannot be explained in the formation of covalent bond between the permeating species and the membrane material since the system under study provides little evidence for such interaction. Such a behaviour can then only be explained by assuming that permeation may not be the rate determining step and permeating molecules are partially immobilised in membrane's structure or in the interfacial region.

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